

Reactivity Monitoring Using Multi-step Least-squares Inverse Kinetics Method

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ABSTRACT

To develop a monitoring technique during the retrieval of fuel debris at the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear power plants, this study proposes the reactivity monitoring method based on the improved simplest reactivity estimator with the multi-step least squares inverse kinetics method (MLK). MLK is used to calibrate the effective source strength for the improved simplest reactivity estimator. By the aid of this calibration, the time variation in the reactivity in dollar units can be inversely estimated by the simplest reactivity estimator in an experimental data-driven way without prior knowledge of the point kinetics parameters. As a preliminary analysis, we apply the proposed method to the experimental results of neutron count rates during the experiment of the approach-to-criticality at the modified STACY, which is a light-water-moderated heterogeneous critical assembly.

Keywords: Reactivity, Inverse Kinetics Method, Least-squares, Modified STACY

1. INTRODUCTION

During the fuel debris retrieval process at the Fukushima Daiichi (1F) nuclear power plants, monitoring techniques are important from the perspective of the defense-in-depth strategy. The previous study [1] estimated that 1F unit 1 was in a deep subcritical state based on Bayesian inference for the radioactivity concentration ratio of ⁸⁸Kr to ¹³⁵Xe in the primary containment vessel (PCV) gas monitor. Note that there is a possibility of inserting the positive reactivity worth due to the change in the H/U moderation ratio by some perturbations during debris retrieval. The analysis results of the first-round sample of fuel debris at 1F unit 2 [2] indicate that the ratio of ²³⁵U/(²³⁴U+²³⁵U+²³⁶U+²³⁸U) was approximately 1.9 at%, which is comparable to that of the core-averaged value just before the severe accident. In the debris sample, the presence of ²⁴⁴Cm was confirmed to be accompanied by U. Therefore, we guess that a certain magnitude of neutron flux is maintained by the subcritical neutron multiplication driven by the ²⁴⁴Cm spontaneous neutron fission source. The monitoring of the neutron count rate during the debris retrieval will provide useful information to ensure that the target system keeps the subcritical state. For example, the inverse kinetics method [3–5] can monitor the reactivity $\rho(t)$ based on the time variation in the neutron count rates $P(t)$ measured by a neutron detector through the appropriate neutron/gamma discrimination.

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However, there are some issues in applying the inverse kinetics method to the 1F situation. One of the issues is that there will be large uncertainties of the point kinetics parameters (e.g., neutron generation time Λ and effective delayed neutron fraction β_{eff}) because the detailed information is not enough for the numerical analysis in advance. Another issue is calibrating the effective source strength on-site. To address these issues, this paper presents a reactivity monitoring technique based on the improved simplest reactivity estimator [5–7] with a new technique of multi-step least-squares inverse kinetics method (hereafter referred to as MLK).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly explains the theory for the improved simplest reactivity estimator [6,7], followed by the proposal of MLK. Section 3 presents the preliminary analysis results of MLK applied to the time variation in neutron count rates measured during the experiment of the approach-to-criticality at the modified STACY [8].

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Improved Simplest Reactivity Estimator

In a source-driven subcritical system, the point kinetics equations are described as follows:

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = \frac{\rho(t) - \beta_{\text{eff}}}{\Lambda} P(t) + \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i C_i(t) + \varepsilon Q_0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} = -\lambda_i C_i(t) + \frac{a_i \beta_{\text{eff}}}{\Lambda} P(t), \quad (2)$$

where $P(t)$ denotes the neutron count rate; $C_i(t)$, λ_i , and $a_i \equiv \beta_i / (\sum_{i=1}^6 \beta_i)$ represent the number of precursors, the decay constant, and the relative abundance (or relative delayed neutron yield) for the i th group delayed neutron, respectively; εQ_0 means the product of the detection efficiency and the source strength of the external neutron source. By dividing Eqs. (1) and (2) by $\beta_{\text{eff}}/\Lambda$ [9] which corresponds to the prompt neutron decay constant at a critical state, and by applying the quasi-static approximation for $P(t)$, the following equations are obtained as the measurement principle of the improved simplest reactivity estimator [6,7]:

$$P(t) = \frac{\bar{A}(t) + S_0}{1 - \rho(t)/\beta_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{A}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^6 a_i \int_{-\infty}^t P(t') e^{-\lambda_i(t-t')} \lambda_i dt', \quad (4)$$

$$S_0 \equiv \frac{\Lambda}{\beta_{\text{eff}}} \varepsilon Q_0, \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{A}(t)$ and S_0 denotes the effective source strength for the delayed neutron precursors and the external neutron source, respectively. Note that the improved simplest reactivity estimator is a variant of the original method [5] to estimate the reactivity in dollar units without the point kinetics parameters.

Let us assume that the time series data of neutron count rates P_n are successively measured during a specific counting gate width Δt ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$). In addition, let us set a_i and λ_i values based on literature data (e.g., the Keepin's delayed neutron data [10]) according to the major fissile nuclide in the target system. Then, if the source strength S_0 can be calibrated in some way, the reactivity in the dollar units $\rho_n/\beta_{\text{eff}}$ can be inversely estimated by measured P_n :

$$\frac{\rho_n}{\beta_{\text{eff}}} = 1 - \frac{\bar{A}_n + S_0}{P_n}, \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{A}_n = \sum_{i=1}^6 a_i A_{i,n}, \quad (7)$$

$$A_{i,n} = A_{i,n-1} e^{-\lambda_i \Delta t} + \left(\frac{1 - e^{-\lambda_i \Delta t}}{\lambda_i \Delta t} - e^{-\lambda_i \Delta t} \right) P_{n-1} + \left(1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda_i \Delta t}}{\lambda_i \Delta t} \right) P_n, \quad (8)$$

where the recurrence relation of Eq. (8) can be derived by assuming the linear approximation for the time variation in P_n . Note that, if the target system is maintained in a steady state, the relationship of $\bar{A}_n = A_{i,n} = P_n$ is satisfied. Therefore, the initial value of $A_{i,0}$ can be given by $A_{i,0} = P_0$ for the initial condition before reactivity transient. Using Eqs. (6)–(8), $\rho_n/\beta_{\text{eff}}$ can be monitoring in the experimental data driven manner without the point kinetics parameters.

2.2. Multi-step Least-squares Inverse Kinetics method (MLK)

To utilize the improved simplest reactivity estimator, the source strength S_0 should be appropriately calibrated. The simplest way is to measure the neutron count rate P_0 for a reference state where the $\rho_0/\beta_{\text{eff}}$ is already known by another method (e.g., reactor noise analysis method using the lag-1 autocovariance [11]). Then, S_0 can be calibrated by $S_0 = (-\rho_0/\beta_{\text{eff}})P_0$ based on Eq. (6).

To establish an alternative way if we cannot measure the reference value of $\rho_0/\beta_{\text{eff}}$, we propose the MLK to calibrate S_0 in an experimental data-driven way. Let us assume that the initial state is kept in a subcritical state where $\rho_0/\beta_{\text{eff}}$ is unknown. For the target subcritical system driven by the external source S_0 , the time series data P_n is measured to monitor the time variation in \bar{A}_n using Eqs. (7) and (8). While monitoring \bar{A}_n , let us consider the occurrence of multiple stepwise reactivity transients in the target system. Then, we can carefully pick up \bar{A}_m and P_m for each time interval where the reactivity maintains a specific constant value of $\rho_s/\beta_{\text{eff}}$ after a sufficient elapsed time following the transient ($s = 1, \dots, NS$ where NS means the total number of stepwise transients). Here, the subscript m corresponds to the selected time steps for the MLK. After this masking process, let us make the scatter plot of (\bar{A}_m, P_m) where the horizontal and vertical axes are \bar{A}_m and P_m , respectively. Finally, the source strength S_0 can be uniquely determined by the non-linear least squares using the following fitting function with $(NS + 1)$ fitting parameters $(S_0, \rho_1/\beta_{\text{eff}}, \dots, \rho_{NS}/\beta_{\text{eff}})$ the for the obtained (\bar{A}_m, P_m) plot:

$$P_m = \sum_{s=1}^{NS} w_s(t_m) \left(\frac{\bar{A}_m + S_0}{1 - \rho_s/\beta_{\text{eff}}} \right), \quad (9)$$

$$w_s(t_m) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if time } t_m \text{ is within the range of the } s\text{th stepwise transient} \\ 0 & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $w_s(t_m)$ is the window function. In this study, the masking process was manually executed; therefore, the development of the automatic masking process is one of the future research topics. For example, an AI-based image recognition technique may be useful to identify the fitting ranges.

3. PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS FOR EXPERIMENTS

3.1. Experimental and Analysis Conditions

In this study, we tried applying MLK to the neutron count rates P_n measured in the experiment of the approach-to-criticality at the modified STACY [8], which is a critical assembly in the Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA). In the modified STACY, the reactivity can be controlled by changing the water level. According to the variation of the water level, the measured time series data P_n increases or decreases. In the experiment of the approach-to-criticality, the Am-Be neutron source was used as the startup neutron source. Figure 1 shows the experimental examples of measured P_n for two different neutron detector channels. In Figure 1, the time series data P_n were collected with $\Delta t = 1$ s and the dead time effect on P_n was not corrected. The bilateral filter [6,12] was applied to the original data P_n in order to reduce the statistical fluctuation of P_n while preserving sharp edges in the time variation of P_n .

Figure 1. Neutron count rates after bilateral filter.

The light-water-moderated core of the modified STACY was configured using cylindrical UO_2 fuel rods with 5 wt% ^{235}U enrichment. Therefore, this study used the Keepin's six-group data for the ^{235}U thermal fission system [10] as a_i and λ_i as shown in Table I. Using Eqs. (7) and (8) with these delayed neutron parameters for measured P_n , the time series data \bar{A}_n were obtained as shown in Figure 2.

To apply MLK to (\bar{A}_m, P_m) data as shown in Figure 2, the fitted data (red points in Figures 1 and 2) were manually determined based on the time variation of P_n after each transient and the ranges satisfying the linearity relationship of Eq. (9). After calibrating S_0 using MLK, the reactivity in dollar units was finally obtained using Eqs. (6)–(8) with S_0 .

Table I. Delayed neutron parameters [10].

delayed neutron precursor group i	relative abundance a_i	decay constant λ_i (s^{-1})
1	0.033	0.0124
2	0.219	0.0305
3	0.196	0.111
4	0.395	0.301
5	0.115	1.14
6	0.042	3.01

 Figure 2. Scatter plots of (\bar{A}_m, P_m) .

3.2. Analysis Results

Figure 3 shows the fitting results of MLK for the selected (\bar{A}_m, P_m) data. In Figure 3, the three lines correspond to the fitted linear function for each stepwise transient. As can be seen from Figure 3, the \bar{A}_m -intercepts, which correspond to the value of $-S_0$, are the same for these three lines by MLK. The S_0 values (approximately 103 and 147 (s^{-1})) are different between the two detector channels because of the difference in their detection efficiencies.

Figure 4 shows the preliminary results of the improved simplest reactivity estimator for the measured neutron count rates P_n shown in Figure 1. Note that, in order to validate the estimated $\rho_n/\beta_{\text{eff}}$, we need to compare them with the reference values. For example, the reference value of $\rho_n/\beta_{\text{eff}}$ can be evaluated based on the reactivity coefficient with respect to the water level and the time series data of the water level. Namely, the following investigations are required: an additional experiment (or a numerical analysis using the continuous energy Monte Carlo code) to determine the reactivity coefficient of the water level; and the real-time monitoring of the water level during the experiment of the approach-to-criticality. Such a detailed discussion will be carried out as a future research topic.

As supplemental information to emphasize the effectiveness of our proposed method, another experimental validation result for UTR-KINKI [13] is shown in Appendix A.

Figure 3. Preliminary results of MLK.

Figure 4. Preliminary results of reactivity in dollar units.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study newly proposed the multi-step least-squares inverse kinetics method (MLK) to calibrate the effective source strength S_0 , which is necessary to inversely estimate the reactivity in dollar units using the improved simplest reactivity estimator. As the preliminary experimental analysis, we applied MLK to the experimental data of neutron count rates measured at the modified STACY. As already described in each section, there are some future research topics to be addressed. To ensure the validity of our proposed method, the comparison with the reference value of ρ/β_{eff} is necessary for the modified STACY. Further improvement of the algorithm in MLK will be investigated to automatically detect the fitting ranges in MLK.

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REFERENCES

1. Y. Morimoto, M. Akaike, S. Takeo, and H. Maruyama, "Proposal of a Statistical Evaluation Method for the Criticality of the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plants," *Nuclear Technology*, **vol. 205**, no. 12, pp. 1652–1660, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1080/00295450.2019.1580529.
2. "Analysis Results for Fuel Debris Samples (First Round)," TEPCO. Accessed: Sep. 21, 2025. [Online.] Available: https://www.tepco.co.jp/decommission/information/committee/roadmap_progress/pdf/2025/d250731_25-j.pdf
3. C. A. Sastre, "The Measurement of Reactivity," *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **vol. 8**, no. 5, pp. 443–447, Nov. 1960, doi: 10.13182/NSE60-A25827.
4. J. E. Hoogenboom and A. R. van der Sluijs, "Neutron Source Strength Determination for On-line Reactivity Measurements," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **vol. 15**, no. 12, pp. 553–559, Jan. 1988, doi: 10.1016/0306-4549(88)90059-X.
5. Y. Shimazu, "A Simple Procedure to Estimate Reactivity with Good Noise Filtering Characteristics," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 73, pp. 392–397, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2014.07.005.
6. T. Moribe, T. Endo, A. Yamamoto, and J. Kaneko, "Investigation of Subcriticality Monitoring Method Using Improved Simplest Reactivity Estimator with Bilateral Filter," in *International Conference on Physics of Reactors (PHYSOR 2024)*, San Francisco, CA: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 97–106. doi: 10.13182/PHYSOR24-43487.
7. C. H. Pyeon, G. Chiba, T. Endo, and K. Watanabe, "Subcriticality Measurements," in *Reactor Laboratory Experiments at Kyoto University Critical Assembly*, Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2025, pp. 199–240. doi: 10.1007/978-981-97-8070-9_10.
8. S. Araki *et al.*, "Integrated Thermal Power Measurement in the Modified Stacy for the Performance Inspections," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **vol. 217**, Art no. 111323, Jul. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2025.111323.
9. T. Endo, A. Nonaka, S. Imai, A. Yamamoto, A. Sakon, and K. Hashimoto, "Subcriticality Measurement Using Time-domain Decomposition-based Integral Method for Simultaneous Reactivity and Source Changes," *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, **vol. 57**, no. 5, pp. 607–616, May 2020, doi: 10.1080/00223131.2019.1706658.
10. G. R. Keepin, T. F. Wimett, and R. K. Zeigler, "Delayed Neutrons from Fissionable Isotopes of Uranium, Plutonium, and Thorium," *Phys. Rev.*, **vol. 107**, no. 4, pp. 1044–1049, Aug. 1957, doi: 10.1103/PhysRev.107.1044.
11. R. Hirota *et al.*, "Absolute Measurement of Subcriticality in Dollar Units Based on Lag-1 Autocovariance of Zero-power Reactor Noise," *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, **vol. 63**, no. 1, pp. 54–65, Jan. 2026, doi: 10.1080/00223131.2025.2530788.
12. C. Tomasi and R. Manduchi, "Bilateral Filtering for Gray and Color Images," in *Sixth International Conference on Computer Vision (IEEE Cat. No.98CH36271)*, Bombay, India: Narosa Publishing House, 1998, pp. 839–846. doi: 10.1109/ICCV.1998.710815.

13. G. Wakabayashi, T. Yamada, T. Endo, and C. H. Pyeon, *Introduction to Nuclear Reactor Experiments*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2023. doi: 10.1007/978-981-19-6589-0.

APPENDIX A

As supplemental information, another experimental validation of our proposed method was separately investigated for the time series data of P_n measured during the experiment of the approach-to-criticality at UTR-KINKI [13], where the reactivity was controlled by the control rod positions. In the case of UTR-KINKI, the reference value of $\rho_n/\beta_{\text{eff}}$ can be evaluated based on the control rod worth and the rod position. The control rod worth for each rod was measured by the rod drop and the period methods [11]. The time-series data of the control rod positions were collected by the virtual console of UTR-KINKI. Figure 5 shows the analysis result of the improved simplest reactivity estimator with MLK, compared to the reference value. Consequently, the estimated $\rho_n/\beta_{\text{eff}}$ by our proposed method was reasonably agreed well with the reference value.

Figure 5. Analysis results of reactivity in dollar units for UTR-KINKI.